

TECHNISCHE
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WIEN

Examine the correlation between Twitter Sentiment data and the stock data of the 4 big tech companies Apple, Amazon, Google and Microsoft

Data Management Plan (DMP)

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Document link:	https://github.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data
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Deliverable abstract
<p>This deliverable is the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Examine the correlation between Twitter Sentiment data and the stock data of the 4 big tech companies Apple, Amazon, Google and Microsoft project, delivered in [M4]. It will be kept updated as a living document. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project according to the principles outlined in the [section name] section.</p>

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	FAIR-Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MB	Megabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created or reused and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#).

Maximilian Kölblbacher (e11708961@student.tuwien.ac.at) will act as the data manager who will be in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

1.2. Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Produced datasets:

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	AAPL_normal_bert.csv	Structured text	csv	100 MB	no
P2	AMZN_normal_bert.csv	Structured text	csv	100 MB	no
P3	GOOGL_normal_bert.csv	Structured text	csv	100 MB	no
P4	GOOGL_social_media_bert.csv	Structured text	csv	100 MB	no
P5	AAPL_social_media_bert.csv	Structured text	csv	100 MB	no
P6	AMZN_social_media_bert.csv	Structured text	csv	100 MB	no
P7	MSFT_social_media_bert.csv	Structured text	csv	100 MB	no
P8	MSFT_normal_bert.csv	Structured text	csv	100 MB	no

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Stock Market Dataset	10.34740/kaggle/dsv/1054465		no
R2	Tweets about the Top Companies from 2015 to 2020	https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/omermetinn/tweets-about-the-top-companies-from-2015-to-2020/data		No

The purpose of using these specific datasets are, the possibilities they give to analyze the stock data changes, based on the sentiment analysis of the previous day. Including this output information it is possible to analyze our goal of searching for possible correlation between those two. The data originally comes from Kaggle, an open source page for all kinds of different datasets.

The outcome of the analysis could be useful for economists, journalists, that report on the Apple stock data and also data scientists, that experiment with text-mining models, and want to optimize models based on additional data.

1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The data "Tweets about the top companies from 2015 to 2020" will be used in order to predict the sentiment with the normal and the social media bert model. This is done by a python project, that calculates the sentiment of every single post. Additionally it gathers the day by day data to analyze the positive, neutral and negative percentage every day. In addition the underlying project uses this generated data and as well as the stock data analysis dataset, to search for a possible correlation between the two datasets. This investigation is done by analyzing different statistical measurements.

1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users

Decision makers in the industry, Journalists

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

The data is findable, by in a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata. The repository will provide means for harvesting the metadata, including its machine-actionable representation. The respective work package leader will handle the structure and versioning of the research data.

As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide xml files with an explanation of all values and terms used at file level. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data. This includes common metadata such as title, description, or keywords when publishing data. The xml files include the necessary metadata in Dublin Core format. These files also include searchable keywords, for discovery and re-use.

As far as possible, controlled vocabulary is used for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

- Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?
- Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?
- Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Data:

- Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.
- If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

- Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?
- If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?
- How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
- Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Metadata:

- Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?
- How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
- Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

The data and the corresponding code is stored in a public repository and necessary arrangements have been taken to keep the data at the following repository (GitHub: <https://github.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data>). Additionally the repository can be identified by a digital object identifier: 10.5281/zenodo.10966852.

The datasets will be available by a standardized protocol (REST protocol).

dataset ID	title	REST HTTP Request Link
P1	AAPL_normal_bert.csv	https://raw.githubusercontent.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data/main/stock_data_analysis/AAPL_normal_bert.csv
P2	AMZN_normal_bert.csv	https://raw.githubusercontent.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data/main/stock_data_analysis/AMZN_normal_bert.csv
P3	GOOGL_normal_bert.csv	https://raw.githubusercontent.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data/main/stock_data_analysis/GOOGL_normal_bert.csv
P4	GOOGL_social_media_bert.csv	https://raw.githubusercontent.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data/main/stock_data_analysis/GOOGL_social_media_bert.csv
P5	AAPL_social_media_bert.csv	https://raw.githubusercontent.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data/main/stock_data_analysis/AAPL_social_media_bert.csv

dataset ID	title	REST HTTP Request Link
P6	AMZN_social_media_bert.csv	https://raw.githubusercontent.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data/main/stock_data_analysis/AMZN_social_media_bert.csv
P7	MSFT_social_media_bert.csv	https://raw.githubusercontent.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data/main/stock_data_analysis/MSFT_social_media_bert.csv
P8	MSFT_normal_bert.csv	https://raw.githubusercontent.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data/main/stock_data_analysis/MSFT_normal_bert.csv

There are no restriction regarding the access of the datasets, neither during nor at the end of the project. This also means that it is not necessary to keep track of people accessing the data and reusing it.

As we are not operating on personal or sensitive data there is no need for the access committee to access the datasets.

We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible and license it with CC0. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	No	2024-02-29	https://github.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data	10.5281/zenodo.10966852	CC-BY-4.0
P2	Open	No	2024-02-29	https://github.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data	10.5281/zenodo.10966852	CC-BY-4.0
P3	Open	No	2024-02-29	https://github.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data	10.5281/zenodo.10966852	CC-BY-4.0
P4	Open	No	2024-02-29	https://github.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data	10.5281/zenodo.10966852	CC-BY-4.0
P5	Open	No	2024-02-29	https://github.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data	10.5281/zenodo.10966852	CC-BY-4.0

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P6	Open	No	2024-02-29	https://github.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data	10.5281/zenodo.10966852	CC-BY-4.0
P7	Open	No	2024-02-29	https://github.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data	10.5281/zenodo.10966852	CC-BY-4.0
P8	Open	No	2024-02-29	https://github.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data	10.5281/zenodo.10966852	CC-BY-4.0

Methods or software needed to access and use data: Specific tools are not necessary, as the output data is in csv file format, which is easy useable (also for non IT experts) and interoperable.

The data as well as the metadata will be available and findable for the next 10 years.

The open source code, that created the data is available and documented to execute in detail through Github: <https://github.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data>

2.3. Making data interoperable

- What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?
- In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow re-using, refining, or extending them?
- Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

The data was made interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain. As far as possible, controlled vocabularies for our data is used to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability. Good documentation for all our datasets and for the execution of the underlying programs is provided in the Readme.

As there is no need to generate new vocabularies and ontologies, mappings are not needed in the scope of this data management.

The project will use also other data, which is necessary for the project execution. This data will be referenced in the readme of the repository.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
- Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
- Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
- Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
- Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
- Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

By adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets we guarantee the reusability of our data. The descriptions includes details on the methodology used, analytical, and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data is assigned and clearly marked. The digital research data obtained will be published Open Access under a Creative Commons CC BY license, provided there are no data protection concerns.

In order to provide the documentation for the dataset a full description of the dataset, including the variables, datatypes, definitions was generated and included in metadata files. Additionally codebooks with a detailed documentation of the code will be provided to reproduce and understand the output in detail. A documentation of the used methodologies will be part of the overall documentation as well. This will include the measurement parameters as well as methodologies used to calculate the reliability of the output.

The data is available and useable by any kind of third party. Therefore an organization for providing the data in a public domain is used. License will be given out by the standard reuse licenses.

Provenance of the data are linked to the necessary location, where the data was originally published. These links are available in the corresponding readme file.

The following data quality checks will be done: repeated samples or measurements. This can and will be done, by running the experiment for upcoming years as well.

The research outputs will also be provided as a report in the same repository as the datasets and the source code.

3. Other research outputs

- In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).
- Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

Other research output and software apart from the datasets, were documented in the report, that is available in the same repository as the data.

Pretraining to the FAIR principles, the additionally data is findable and accessible with the same DOI as the datasets as all is stored in the same repository structure. The keywords in the metadata files will help to ensure findability of the additional data. Interoperability will only be guaranteed as far as the generation of the project, the datasets and the metadata goes. Interoperability with the report is not guaranteed. Proper documentation and keeping the files up-to-date ensures reusability of the code and the datasets. Additional licenses, that are added to the repository ensure the permission of reusing the output.

4. Allocation of resources

- What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?
- How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)
- Who will be responsible for data management in your project?
- How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
Storage		Costs to store the data	<100MB	0
Reuse		Keep data reuseable	€	0

Security		Backups and protection of data	€	0
Archiving		Archiving the data	€	0
Estimated total costs				0

Coverage of costs: = 0,00€

As the project manager takes care of Storage, Reuse, Security and Archiving, no costs need to be played for work. Additionally as datasets are very small, providing them do not result in any costs as well.

The data manager will direct the data management process overall being responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

5. Data security

- What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
- Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

5.1. Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager.

R1 (Stock Market Dataset), R2 (Tweets about the Top Companies from 2015 to 2020) will be stored on Github: GitHub is an application for managing repositories based on Git provided and managed by Microsoft. The owner of the project manages the repository, assign project permissions, and appoint external project partners as additional users.

5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies.

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	reading only
P2	writing	writing	reading only
P3	writing	writing	reading only
P4	writing	writing	reading only
P5	writing	writing	reading only
P6	writing	reading only	reading only
P7	writing	writing	reading only
P8	writing	writing	reading only
R1	reading only	reading only	reading only
R2	reading only	reading only	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)
P1	https://github.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data/tree/main/stock_data_analysis	10 years
P2	https://github.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data/tree/main/stock_data_analysis	10 years
P3	https://github.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data/tree/main/stock_data_analysis	10 years
P4	https://github.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data/tree/main/stock_data_analysis	10 years
P5	https://github.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data/tree/main/stock_data_analysis	10 years

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)
P6	https://github.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data/tree/main/stock_data_analysis	10 years
P7	https://github.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data/tree/main/stock_data_analysis	10 years
P8	https://github.com/mkoe97/Examine-the-correlation-between-Twitter-Sentiment-data-and-stock-data/tree/main/stock_data_analysis	10 years

6. Ethical and legal issues

- Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
- Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

6.1. Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

6.2. Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.

6.3. Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

7. Other issues

